

CO-CONTINUOUS METAL/CERAMIC COMPOSITES MADE BY REACTIVE METAL PENETRATION OF COMMERCIAL ALUMINIUM ALLOYS INTO CORDIERITE

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ABSTRACT

Co-continuous metal/ceramic composites (or C⁴) were obtained by Reactive Metal Penetration starting from commercial cordierite preforms. The infiltrating alloys were chosen to be 1050, 2011 and 7075 standard aluminium alloys, with increasing content of alloying elements. The kinetics of infiltration was studied, together with the microstructure and mechanical properties of the obtained composites, which are influenced by the quantity of alloying elements. The higher the alloying elements quantity, the higher the microhardness of the composites.

Keywords: metal-ceramic composites; co-continuous structure; reactive infiltration; cordierite; aluminium alloys.

Introduction

Reactive Metal Penetration is a near net shape process that implies a displacement reaction between a liquid metal, generally aluminium, and an oxide precursor (usually a silicate). The liquid alloy simultaneously reacts and penetrates the ceramic preform, leaving behind a metal/ceramic composite in which the phases are continuous and interpenetrated [1-8].

The high ceramic content (around 65% in vol.) of these composites together with the thermal conductivity of the metallic network, make them attractive for wear resistant components [9-11]. Moreover the possibility of tailoring the properties through a convenient choice of low cost precursors open new horizons for the applications of these kind of composites.

While traditionally silica glass was used as a preform, recently C⁴ were produced starting from commercial cordierite items and pure aluminium [12]. This composite showed mechanical properties slightly inferior to those silica-derived, but with a reduction of costs. The natural development of this was to consider to employ some commercial aluminium alloys, instead of more expensive pure Al, also trying to enhance some mechanical properties, in particular hardness.

In this work we employed three different aluminium alloys, standard designated as 1050, 2011 (rich in Cu) and 7075 (rich in Zn and Mg). The total content of alloying

elements increases from 1050 to 2011 and to 7075. The produced composites were then analysed in terms of microstructure and mechanical properties.

Experimental procedure

The reaction of cordierite preforms with the molten aluminium alloy took place at 1200 °C in air. In the case of cordierite and pure Al the reaction was the following:

By operating in excess of Al, the Si dissolved in the bath, and the final composite was made of a silicon-rich aluminium alloy, alumina, magnesium-aluminium spinel, and a potassium hexaaluminate, as observed in previous works [12].

In this work commercial pure cordierite was used, produced by Petroceramics S.r.l. by uniaxial pressing of atomised powders and subsequent sintering in bars of 150 x 11 x 8 mm size or rods of 8 mm diameter and 80 mm length . The presence of some impurities in the ceramic preforms, represented by Fe, K and Na (determined by EDS analysis) plays a significant role in the infiltration process. As stated above and reported in the work of Pavese and co. [13], they are responsible for the hexaaluminate phase formation.

The three aluminium alloys considered as infiltrating ones derived from semi-finished products: sheets for 1050, bars for 2011 and 7075, furnished by Co.Me.Fi. Metalli S.r.l., Torino. In Table 1 is presented the nominal chemical compositions of the employed aluminium alloys, that was also confirmed by EDS and fluorescence measurements.

Table 1 Nominal compositions of 1050, 2011 and 7075 aluminium alloys [13].

Aluminium alloy	Si	Fe	Cu	Mg	Zn	Al min.
1050 (% in wt.)	< 0.25	< 0.45	< 0.10	< 0.05	< 0.10	99.50
2011 (% in wt.)	< 0.40	< 0.70	5.0-6.0	-	< 0.30	remainder
7075 (% in wt.)	< 0.40	< 0.50	1.2-2.0	2.1-2.9	5.1-6.1	remainder

During the process, the ceramic samples were immersed in the molten metal for 3 hours, then the temperature bath was taken down to 850 °C and the composites were extracted and cooled in calm air. The samples were then cleaned from any residual aluminium by a 320 grit-size abrasive paper.

The microstructure of composites was investigated mainly by a Scanning Electron Microscope Leo 1450 VP, combined with Oxford 7353 EDS analysis for assessing chemical composition. X-ray microdiffraction (D/max RAPID, with spot size of 100 µm diameter) was also used as a check in determining the phases present in the composites.

For evaluating their mechanical properties, Vickers microhardness measurements (load 500 g) were performed on the cross section of composite samples, while elastic modulus

was evaluated by an impulse excitation technique, by means of GrindoSonic MK5 instrument. The composites were also submitted to three-point bending tests, performed using a Sintech 10D equipment (in stroke control with crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min).

Kinetics

To make a comparison with traditional silica glass preform, long-term infiltration experiments (up to 8 hours) were performed using the three aluminium alloys and both silica and cordierite samples.

With this purpose, cylindrical samples of 8 mm diameter and 80 mm length were partially immersed in an upright position in the metal bath (one for each alloy) at 1200 °C, with the melt line of the bath located at the mid-point of the precursor: half of the rod is immersed, and half is out in the open air. In this manner, the infiltration proceeded with the metal growing up into the preform, and it was possible to determine the infiltration length: with a digital camera a series of photographs of the system were taken at regular time intervals, allowing to measure the infiltrated height of samples.

The experimental values acquired are plotted in Figure 1. Considering silica preforms, the rate of infiltration are similar for 1050 and 2011 alloys, while there is a small increase with 7075 alloy, thanks to the presence of magnesium, as observed in previous works [14].

Figure 1: infiltration length of silica (filled points) and cordierite (void points) samples with the three aluminium alloys versus time of infiltration.

In the case of cordierite the behaviour is different: it seems that copper provokes an acceleration of the reaction, while magnesium a rate reduction. In literature is reported that magnesium slows down the infiltration of mullite [4], but the role of copper is not yet investigated.

Microstructure analysis

To investigate the microstructure of these composites, samples were cross-sectioned and polished down to 3 μm diamond paste.

In composites derived from infiltrations using 1050 and 2011 alloys we can detect two different types of microstructure. The external zone, the first to be infiltrated, is characterized by interconnected nearly spherical grains of alumina (lighter), surrounded by the metal network (darker), as reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: microstructure of the external zone of composites obtained by infiltration with 1050 alloy.

In the core, the ceramic phase becomes a very fine mixture of Mg spinel (grey grains) and potassium hexaaluminate (grey needle shaped grains), intermingled with a smaller metal network (the darker one) as shown in Figure 3.

This is probably due to a higher concentration of K impurities in the last infiltrated zone; this element is not involved in the reaction and tend to accumulate at the reaction front. Also magnesium is partially drawn away from the surface of the sample during infiltration, since in the external layer only alumina and aluminium are present. When

the preform is wholly reacted, the concentration of impurities is locally very high and the formation of new phases is possible.

Figure 3: microstructure of the centre of composites obtained by infiltration with 1050 alloy.

In the case of composite derived from 2011 alloy, EDS measurements confirmed that Cu exists only in the aluminium network but it is not present in the ceramic phase.

Considering composites obtained with 7075 alloy, the microstructure is very different: in this case, Figure 4, the external region is made of magnesium spinel, present both as coarser grains and finer ones, and aluminium alloy (again the darker phase).

The alumina grains begin to appear only going toward the centre of samples, and in the core there is a mixture of magnesium spinel, needle-shaped hexaaluminate grains, aluminium alloy and alumina (Figure 5).

Figure 4: microstructure of the external zone of composites obtained by infiltration with 7075 alloy.

Figure 5: microstructure of the centre of composites obtained by infiltration with 7075 alloy.

Mechanical properties

The composites obtained by infiltration with 1050 alloy present good overall mechanical properties: a bending strength over 200 MPa and a Young's Modulus around 150 GPa. Due to a different dimensional porous distribution, the other two infiltrating alloys bring to composites with similar Young's Modulus but lower flexural strength.

On the other side, the results of Vickers microhardness measurements show that the hardness increases with the increase of alloying elements in the infiltrating alloy, as reported in Table 2. The microhardness of these composites was evaluated both in the external area of the composites and in the core, since where needle-shape phases are formed, a marked increase of hardness is observed.

Table 2 Vickers microhardness values of C⁴ composites obtained by cordierite infiltration with different aluminium alloys.

Infiltrating alloy	HV (500g) – external zone	HV (500g) - core
1050	300	660
2011	470	630
7075	700	815

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